

Characterization and Dielectric Properties of LaMnO₃ Nanofibers

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Abstract

A new approach, combining sol-gel process with electrospinning technique was used to prepare LaMnO₃/PVA composite nanofibers. In this research work, LaMnO₃ nanopowders were firstly prepared by calcination of composite carbonate at 1000 °C for 30 min. Electrospinning technique has been extensively explored as a simple and versatile method for drawing nanofibers from polymer solutions. LaMnO₃ / PVA perovskite-type nanofibers were obtained after annealed at 500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C for 2 h respectively. Novel polycrystalline LaMnO₃ nanofibers were yielded at different temperatures as the final products. Phase formation and crystal structure of LaMnO₃ nanopowders were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD). Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FESEM) images revealed that LaMnO₃ as-spun nanofibers on Al foils were attracted to be in the range of 60 nm to 120 nm in diameters with electrospinning set-up for 20 min. The modification and functionalize sample surface at a nanometer range of LaMnO₃ nanofibers were examined by Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM). The dielectric properties of LaMnO₃ nanofibers were identify by C-f, ϵ_r -f, $\tan \delta$ -f and σ_{ac} -f characteristics. The qualifications of LaMnO₃ nanofibers were successfully yielded by the electrospinning technique as final products. The results obtained from this research will lead to enable new levels of electronic applications, biomedical applications and protective clothing as the field of nanotechnology.

Key words: Electrospinning set-up, LaMnO₃ Nanofibers, XRD, FESEM and AFM.

Introduction

In recent years, nanotechnology has become one of the most important and popular fields in research area of science subjects. On nanoscale, chemistry, physics, biology, electronic, material science and engineering subjects start to converge and the distinctions as to which property a particular discipline contribute to understanding and exploiting the possibilities offered by nanotechnology. Nanoscale materials have been used for many decades in several applications and opportunities (Reneker and Chun, 1995).

Polymeric nanofibers can be made using the electrospinning process, which has been described in the literature and in patents. Electrospinning is a relatively simple technique to produce nanofibers from polymer solutions. Electrospinning uses an electric field to draw a polymer melt or polymer solution from the tip of a capillary to a collector. The electrospinning process has been documented using a variety of polymers (Doshi and Renker, 1995; Chun, et al, 1999). Nanofibers are successfully grown by electrospinning method as a non-woven mat. Nanofibers can be identified as fibers having diameter between tens and hundreds of nanometers (Srinivasan, et al, 1995; Sauter, 2005). The electrospinning process is an interesting and well-investigated physical phenomenon and has been an attractive subject for theoretical investigations an attractive subject for theoretical investigations of several groups. Nowadays, electrospun nanofibers have many advantages such as filtrations, affinity membranes, recovery of metal ions, tissue engineering scaffolds, energy storage sensors and protective clothing (Fang et al 2008). Nanofibers of electrostatic polymers have received great attention recently because of their unique and useful properties. New and unrelated properties may arise from size confinement which may be important for several applications in electronic devices, optics and biomedical materials (Mac Diarmid, et al 2001; Yun, et al, 2004; Wnek, et al, 2003). Nanotechnology is the engineering of systems and materials at the molecular scale.

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As far as nanomaterials are concerned LaMnO_3 nanofibers is one of the candidates which has been attracting due to its numerous interesting properties (Barnabe, et al, 2004). Perovskite-type LaMnO_3 have attracted a great interest for the development of environment friendly catalytic materials. At high temperature, LaMnO_3 has simple cubic perovskite type. Based on this type, LaMnO_3 nanofibers were successfully characterized by electrospinning technique (Kotomin, 2003; Heifets, 1998; Amoroso, et al, 2005).

Experimental

Electrospinning Technique for LaMnO_3 Nanofibers

Electrospinning is a technique that can be used to produce nanofibers under the influence of a high electric field. With the production of nanofibers, nanotechnology extends its application to a vast area. Nanofibers can be made of Lanthanum Manganite by electrospinning technique. Local-made electrospinning set-up was firstly constructed. The high voltage applied in this work was 10 kV~30 kV. The local-made electrospinning apparatus contained a needle or spinneret, high voltage power supply and a grounded collector. It was known by using high voltage probe that produces maximum voltage 30 kV but the operating voltage was 27 kV. A syringe holder and a collector were kept in the cylindrical shape of glass tube, length of 36.3 cm, outside diameter was 9 cm and inside diameter was 8.45 cm. DC voltage generator of positive terminal was connected with hypodermic needle (0.55 mm x 25 mm) and the circular shape of Al collector which was connected by negative terminal of power supply as system ground. In order to create an electric field the system must contain along with the charged needle, a grounded plate. This conductive plate completes a circuit and allows a strong electric field to be created between the needle and the plates. This grounded plate also serves as the collector for the completed nanofiber web that is fabricated during the electrospinning process. The schematic diagram of electrospinning set-up was shown in Figure 1.

Sample Preparation of LaMnO_3 Nanofibers

In this study, Lanthanum Manganite (LaMnO_3) and poly vinyl alcohol (PVA) and distilled water were chosen as the starting chemicals and solvent. LaMnO_3 nanofibers were formed by calcinating preparation of composite fibers, sol-gel process was used. 0.75 g of LaMnO_3 was mixed in 15 g of alcohol (PVA). These mixtures were dissolved in 50 cc of distilled water at room temperature. Then these solutions were stirred vigorously to get the homogeneous precursor sol-gel by magnetic stirrer for 3 h at room temperature. After stirring, the temporary solutions were kept at room temperature for 24 h, a viscous get of PVA/ LaMnO_3 composite was obtained, and that sol-gel was determined by measuring its viscosity. The result of LaMnO_3 sol-gel was to be 1200 cP. The solution gel was expected to be viscous enough for electorspinning. Before setting the vacuum glass-ambient, the experimental set-up was prepared. The hypodermis syringe needle was connected to the positive terminal of a high DC voltage generator that produce maximum voltage 27 kV and the negative terminal of the power supply was connected to the collector (Al foil) opposite to the syringe needle with a distance about 9 cm. Al-substrate was then struck on the collector. Before supplying the power, glass tube was created as vacuum condition by using vacuum pump and also tested by vacuum tester. In the electrospinning process, a high voltage was applied to create an electrically charged jet of colloidal solution which solidified to leave a fiber. One electrode was placed into the spinning solution and the other attached to a colloidal solution. This induced a charge on the surface of the liquid. In this way a charged jet of liquid was ejected from the tip of the capillary tube. A voltage was applied to the polymer solution which causes a jet of the solution to be drawn toward a grounded collector. The fiber jets dry to form polymeric fibers, which can be collected on a web. The electrospinning process has been documented using a variety of

LaMnO₃ nanofibers forming polymers. And then, it was heat-treated at 500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C for 2 h respectively. The block diagram of sample preparation for LaMnO₃ nanofibers was shown in Figure 2.

Figure1. Schematic diagram of electrospinning Set-up

Figure 2. Block diagram of preparation for LaMnO₃ nanofibers

Results and Discussion

XRD Analysis of LaMnO₃ sample

The lanthanum manganite (LMO) nano-powder was obtained and XRD technique was used to examine toward studying phase analysis, powder structure, crystallographic investigation and lattice parameters. XRD was performed using monochromatic CuK α radiation ($\lambda = 1.54056\text{\AA}$) operated at 40 kV (tube voltage) and 20 μA (tube current). Sample was scanned from 10° to 70° in diffraction angle 2θ with a step-size of 0.02°. XRD measurement of LaMnO₃ nanopowder was shown in figure 3. There was extra peaks on pattern of all powders because the results clearly proved the influence of the solvents on the product composition and agreed with the typical LaMnO₃ pattern of perovskite structure. All peaks were found to be well matched with the diffracted of standard. The intensity of (020) reflection was much stronger than that of remaining LaMnO₃ peaks. The XRD measurement showed that all peaks of LaMnO₃ were consisted with that LaMnO₃ standard (JCPDS) powder having an orthorhombic structure. The average crystallite size of LaMnO₃ powders were in the range of 42.39 nm. By analyzing XRD measurement, all the peak heights and peak positions were in good agreement with library file of XRD machine.

Figure 3. XRD patterns of LaMnO₃ nanopowder at 1000 °C

FESEM Analysis of LaMnO₃ Nanofibers

The PVA/LMO composite fibers on aluminium foil were carried out to examine by FESEM images. In order to study the morphology and nano structural properties of fabricated LMO nanofibers were depicted in Figure 4(a-d). These figures showed the FESEM micrographs with the respective diameter histograms of the as-prepared and calcined PVA/LMO composite nanofibers. The as-spun composite nanofibers appeared quite smooth and each individual nanofiber was quite uniform in cross section. These nanofibers were found in the formation of aligned structure. The diameter of nanofibers calcined at 500 °C was ~ 65-70 nm in Figure 4(a). After calcinations at above 500 °C, the nanofibers remained as continuous structure and their diameter appeared to be increased with increasing calcinations temperature at 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C. In contrast, the image of the nanofibers calcined at 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C showed in Figures 5 (b-d) that each fiber contains small LMO particles of ~75-78 nm, ~85-95 nm and ~110-120 nm in diameter. According these results, the morphology and size of the fiber varied strongly with increased of calcinations temperature. The diameter of the fibers increasing and the surface changes rough gradually after sintered at 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C for 2 h respectively. The average diameter of the precursor's LMO nanofibers was found between 60 nm ~ 120 nm. With the temperature of calcinations increased gradually fiber diameter was thicker and fiber surface was extremely rough. This is due to that fiber composition at the beginning was composed of small grains and with the rise of temperature small grain grew up to a large grain and large grain grew again toward surround. When the temperature reached 800 °C which observed that the long-grain completely grew together and the diameter of the fibers were increased ~120 nm. Therefore, LaMnO₃ nanofibers with good morphology and suitable nanometer in diameter should be prepared at low calcinations temperature. The variation in diameter of the fibers with different temperatures for 20 min was shown in Figure 5. The average diameter and morphological properties of LaMnO₃ nanofibers are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Structural properties of LaMnO₃ nanofibers (t=20 min)

No.	Annealing Temperature (°C)	Fiber Diameter (nm)	Morphological Structure
1	500	60	-aligned -smooth -prominent
2	600	78	-single nanofiber -random orientation -smooth
3	700	95	- aligned structure -a little rough
4	800	120	-non-uniform, rough surface -normally vertical and parallel with each fiber

AFM Analysis of LaMnO₃ Nanofibers

Atomic force microscopy (AFM) can be employed as instrument which is suitable to modify and functionalize sample surface at a nanometer range. By using AFM, we were able to analyze the effects of various nanofibers on the nano scale surface structure of LaMnO₃ sample. An AFM scan of LaMnO₃ nanofibers on Al foil were depicted in figure 6 (a-d). Showed comparatively rough surface the polycrystalline nanofibers specific to each strain were

realized on the nanoscale through AFM imaging, thus providing a better understanding of the structural morphology of these nanofibers. The correlation of these nanoscale variations in LaMnO_3 nanofibers were investigated by conducting a surface roughness analysis. The illumination and shadowing showed a quite natural looking surface topography.

Figure 4. FESEM image of LaMnO_4 nanofibers at (a) 500°C; (b) 600°C; (c) 700°C and (d) 800°C.

Figure 5. Temperature dependence of LaMnO_3 nanofibers ($t = 20$ min)

The scan areas of AFM deflection mode images are ($4.11 \mu\text{m} \times 4.11 \mu\text{m}$, $16.6 \mu\text{m} \times 16.4 \mu\text{m}$, $1.30 \mu\text{m} \times 1.03 \mu\text{m}$, $16.6 \mu\text{m}$, $16.4 \mu\text{m}$) of fibers showing palisade like fibers with extended chains. Higher resolution scans of individual nanofibers were shown two highly protrusive parallel bands (scale bar 750 nm) in their nanoscale ultra structure. To avoid sample damage, the microscope was operated in non-contact mode using silicon tips (resistivity 0.01- 0.02 Ωm) from AFM images a uniform agglomeration of well defined, small particles was observed. The grains were elongated along the direction of the withdrawal of the Al substrate from the solutions, during the fibers formation. AFM images showed that the average grains size of deposited LaMnO_3 nanofibers were ranged from (60 nm-100 nm) at different temperatures. The roughness profiles (R_{rms}) of the fiber surfaces have been measured to be in the range of 1.41 nm to 1.45 nm. These values were smaller than those reported in the literature at 2 nm - 4 nm. The roughness measured was less than 5 nm, thus indicating that the nanofibers were optically smooth and good morphology.

Dielectric Characteristics of LaMnO_3 Nanofibers

For most applications of electronic materials, the dielectric constant, dielectric loss and AC conductivity are important practical parameters, so studies of their properties dielectric are basically electric insulators which ordinarily do not contain any free charge carriers for conduction.

The change in capacitance, dielectric constant, dielectric loss and AC conductivity as a function of applied frequency modes (1 – 100 kHz) at zero bias voltage of LaMnO_3 nanofibers by using copper electrodes were investigated. The variation of capacitances, dielectric constant, dielectric loss factors and AC conductivity with frequencies are identified for all different temperatures of LaMnO_3 nanofibers. The dielectric constants were calculated from the capacitances measured without a bias voltage it was clearly observed that step-like capacitance decay is crushed over applied frequency. Decreasing dielectric constant is observed with increasing in frequency for Cu electrode. The decrease in dielectric constant arises from the fact that polarization does not occur instantaneously with the application of the electric field as charges have inertia.

Dissipation factor (D factor) is a measure of the losses of the capacitor under AC operation. At higher frequencies, $\tan \delta$ decreases with increasing frequency because of the active component of the current is practically independent of frequency and the relative component increases in proportion to the frequency. But the other fact of getting lower dielectric and higher lose current is that AC conductivity is rising with frequency. From the graphs, it were seen that $\tan \delta$ value was minimum the fiber at 500 °C and maximum the fiber at 800 °C. The largest value of dielectric constant for LaMnO_3 nanofibers was found at 500 °C and the smallest was at 800 °C. LaMnO_3 nanofibers were measured C-f, ϵ_r -f, $\tan \delta$ -f and σ_{ac} -f variations with different temperatures by LCR analyzer as shown in Figure 7 (a-d).

Figure 6. AFM image of LaMnO_3 nanofibers at (a) 500 °C; (b) 600 °C; (c) 700 °C and (d) 800 °C

Figure 7. Frequency dependence on (a) capacitance; (b) dissipation factor; (c) dielectric constant and (d) conductivity of LaMnO₃ nanofibers at different temperatures

Conclusion

Nanofibers of LaMnO₃ have been successfully fabricated by using an electrospinning and sol-gel technique. Polycrystalline LaMnO₃ nanofibers (diameter of 60-120 nm) as confirmed by FESEM were formed after calcinations of the as-spun PVA/LaMnO₃ composite nanofibers in at 500 °C, 600 °C, 700 °C and 800 °C for 2 h respectively. According to FESEM images, with the temperatures of calcination increased gradually, fiber diameter was thicker and fiber surface was extremely rough. Therefore the crystal structure and morphology of the nanofibers were influenced by the calcination temperatures. AFM analysis revealed that the fibers deposited were crystalline and consisted of grains with the grain size about 20 nm, 25 nm, 30 nm and 34 nm respectively at different temperatures. The roughness of LaMnO₃ fiber surfaces were examined to be in the range of 1.41 nm to 1.45 nm. These values were successfully indicated that the nanofibers were optically smooth and good morphology. The variation of capacitance, dielectric constant, dielectric loss and AC conductivity as a function of applied frequency for LaMnO₃ nanofibers were successfully investigated at zero bias conditions. According to the results obtained, it was seen that dielectric loss values were minimum for the fiber at 500 °C while the maximum value of the fiber was occurred at 800 °C.

The convenience of producing nanofibers should be useful new functional opportunities with the advantage of low cost, biomedical applications and nano-composites.

References

- Amoruso, S., et al, (2005), *Appl. Surf. Sci.*, **248**, 45
- Barnabe. A ., et al, (2004), "Low Temperature Synthesis and Structural Characterization of Over Stoichiometric LaMnO₃ Perovskite," *Materials Research Bulletin*, **39**, 725-735
- Chun, I., et al, (1999), "Carbon Nanofibers from Polyacrylonitrile and Mesophase Pitch", *Journal of Advanced Materials*, **31**(1), 36-41
- Doshi, J. and Reneker, D.H., (1995), "Electrospinning Process and Applications of Electrospun fibers", *Journal of Electrostatics*, **35**, 151-160
- Fung, J., et al, (2008), "Applications of Electrospun Nanofibers", Volume **53**, Number 15, 2265-86
- Heifets, E., et al, (1998), *J. Phys. Cond. Matter*, **10**, 347
- Kotomin, E.A., et al, (2003), *Phys. Chem. Phys.*, **5**, 4180
- Mac Diarmid, A.G., et al, (2001), *Synthetic Metals*, **119**, 27
- Reneker, D.H. and Chun, I., (1996), "Nanometre Diameter Fibers of Polymer, Produced by Electrospinning" *Nanotechnology*, **7**, 216-233
- Sautter, B.P., (2005), "Continuous Polymer Nanofibres using Electrospinning" PhD Thesis, Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Illinois, Chicago
- Srinivasan, G., et al, (1995), *Plym. Int.*, **36**(2), 195-201
- Wnek, G.E., et al, (2003), *Nano Letters*, **3**, 213
- Yun, M.H., et al, (2004), *Nano Letters*, **4**, 419